

Article

Majorana CP-violating Phase Effect on the Effective Electron Neutrino Mass

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Abstract: Implication of the neutrino oscillation search for the neutrino mass square difference and mixing are discussed. We have considered the effective majorana mass m_{ee} , related for $\beta\beta_{0\nu}$ decay. We discuss the effects of majorana phases in effective neutrino masses, it is shown that the majorana phase of the neutrino mixing matrix can affect on effective neutrino masses.

Keywords: effective neutrino mass, majorana phase, majorana mass

1. Introduction

Neutrino mass and mixings is experimentally well confirmed, therefore the theoretical understanding of these quantities is one of the most important issues for particle. Effects of Majorana phase of the neutrino mixing in neutrino oscillation experiment describe by superposition of different neutrino favor. Earlier paper [1,2,3,4,5] describe the Majorana phase do not have any effect in neutrino oscillation in vacuum and matter. . In this paper, we discuss the possible effects of majorona phases on effective neutrino mass.

The neutrino oscillation probabilities in general depend on six parameters two independent mass squared difference Δ_{21} and Δ_{31} , there mixing angle, θ_{12} , θ_{13} , θ_{23} and one CP violating phase δ . There are two large mixing angle θ_{12} , θ_{23} and one small (θ_{13}); and two mass square difference $\Delta_{ij} = m_j^2 - m_i^2$; with M_{ij} the neutrino masses. The angle θ_{12} and θ_{23} represent the neutrino mixing angles corresponding to solar and atmospheric neutrino oscillation. Much progress has been made towards determining the values of the three mixing angle. The outline of the article is as follows. In Section 2, we briefly discuss

neutrino mixing angles and neutrino mass squared differences. In Section 3, we discuss about effective electron neutrino masses. In Section 4, we discuss about numerical results. In Section 4, we present our conclusions.

2. Mixing Angles and Neutrino Mass Squared Differences

The first evidence is the observation of zenith-angle dependence of atmospheric neutrino defect [6] dependent of the atmospheric neutrino $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$ transition with the mass difference and the mixing as

$$\Delta_{31} = (1 - 2) \times 10^{-3} eV^2, \sin^2 2\theta_{23} = 1.0. \quad (1)$$

From the recent three neutrino analysis of the Super-Kamiokande data [12] the following 90% CI were found for the normal (inverted) neutrino mass spectrum

$$1.9(1.7) \times 10^{-3} eV^2 \leq \Delta_{31} \leq 2.6(2.7) \times 10^{-3} eV^2 \quad (2)$$

The second evidence is the solar neutrino deficit [7], which is consistent with $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\tau/\nu_e$ transition. The SNO experiments [8] are consistent with the standard solar model [9] and strongly suggest the LMA solution.

$$\Delta_{21} = 7 \times 10^{-5} eV^2, \sin^2 2\theta_{12} = 0.8. \quad (3)$$

Solar neutrino experiments (Super-K, GALLEX, SAGE, SNO and GNO) show the neutrino oscillations, neutrino oscillation provide the most elegant explanation of all the data [10].

$$\Delta_{solar} = 7_{-1.3}^{+5} \times 10^{-5} eV^2, \quad (4)$$

$$\tan^2 \theta_{solar} = 0.4_{-0.1}^{+0.14}. \quad (5)$$

From the three neutrino global analysis of the solar and reactor KamLAND data was found [14] ,

$$\Delta_{21} = 7.5_{-2.0}^{+1.9} \times 10^{-3} eV^2, \quad \tan^2 \theta_{12} = 0.452_{-0.032}^{+0.035}. \quad (6)$$

Atmospheric neutrino experiments (Kamiokande, Super-K) also show the neutrino oscillation. The most excellent fit to the all data [10].

$$\Delta_{atmo} = 2.0_{-0.92}^{+1.0} \times 10^{-3} eV^2, \quad (7)$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{atmo} = 0.4_{-0.10}^{+0.14}. \quad (8)$$

The CHOOZ reactor experiment [11] gives the upper bound on the third mixing angle θ_{13} as

$$\sin^2\theta_{13} < 0.20 \quad \text{for} \quad |\Delta_{31}| = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} eV^2, \quad (9)$$

$$\sin^2\theta_{13} < 0.16 \quad \text{for} \quad |\Delta_{31}| = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} eV^2, \quad (10)$$

$$\sin^2\theta_{13} < 0.14 \quad \text{for} \quad |\Delta_{31}| = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} eV^2, \quad (11)$$

at the 90 % CL. The CP phase δ has not been constrained. From the two neutrino analysis of the MINOS data obtained was [13] ,

$$\sin^2\theta_{13} < 0.90 \quad \text{for} \quad |\Delta_{31}| = (2.43 \pm 0.13) \times 10^{-3} eV^2, \quad (12)$$

The future neutrino experiments plan to measure the oscillation parameters precisely.

3. Effective Majorona Mass of Electron Neutrino

In the presence of three flavour neutrino mixing the electron neutrino is combination of mass eigenstate, ν_i with eigenvalue m_i

$$\nu_e = \sum U_{ej}\nu_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (13)$$

Here U_{ei} are the elements of the mixing matrix, which relates the flavour states to the mass eigenstates. The $\beta\beta_{0\nu}$ decay rate is determined by the effective Majorana mass of the electron neutrino m_{ee} . Under the assumption of three flavour neutrino mixing of neutrino, the effective Majorana neutrino mass [15] m_{ee} is

$$\begin{aligned} |m_{ee}| &= \left| \sum |U_{ej}|^2 e^{i\phi_j} m_j \right| \\ &= |c_{13}^2 c_{12}^2 m_1 + c_{13}^2 s_{12}^2 e^{i\phi_2} m_2 + s_{13}^2 e^{i\phi_3} m_3|. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Where

$|U_{ej}|, j=1,2,3$ are the absolute values of the elements of the first row of neutrino mixing matrix,

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} c_{12}c_{13} & s_{12}c_{13} & s_{13}e^{-i\delta} \\ -s_{12}c_{23} - c_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & c_{12}c_{23} - s_{12}s_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & s_{23}c_{13} \\ s_{12}s_{23} - c_{12}c_{23}s_{13}e^{i\delta} & -c_{12}s_{23} - s_{12}s_{13}s_{23}e^{i\delta} & c_{23}s_{13} \end{pmatrix},$$

here $c_{ij} = \cos\theta_{ij}, s_{ij} = \sin\theta_{ij}$. The angle ϕ_2, ϕ_3 are the two majorana CP phase. The masses of the vacuum eigenstates are takes to be m_1, m_2 and m_3 . On squaring eq(14),

$$|m_{ee}|^2 = A^2 m_1^2 + B^2 m_2^2 + C^2 m_3^2 + 2AB m_1 m_2 \cos\phi_2 + 2AC m_1 m_3 \cos\phi_3 + 2BC m_3 m_2 \cos(\phi_2 - \phi_3), \tag{15}$$

where $A = c_3^2 c_2^2, B = c_3^2 s_2^2, C = s_3^2$

4. Numerical Results

In tables 1 to 4, we list the effective neutrino mass m_{ee} for $\delta=0$ and $\delta=90$, using the best fit value of oscillation parameter. For the computation purposes, the majorana phases are taken as α and β . We have varied α, β from 0-180 in case of $\delta=0$ and $\delta=90$ respectively.

The variation in m_{ee} is quite small in comparison to $\delta = 0$ and $\delta = 90$. We compute the effective neutrino mass using Eq (15). The result also presented graphically.

Table 1: Effective Neutrino mass for Normal Mass hierarchy and Minimum CP Violating case. Input value are given in ref[16]

Majorana phase	Majorana phase	Effective neutrino masses
α in degrees	β in degrees	m_{ee} in eV
0	0	1.99996
0	45	1.98275
0	90	1.94058
0	135	1.89747
0	180	1.87932
45	0	1.8721
45	45	1.86523
45	90	1.82864
45	135	1.78282
45	180	1.75488
90	0	1.51971
90	45	1.52123
90	90	1.49059
90	135	1.44454
90	180	1.40991
135	0	1.05559
135	45	1.05778
135	90	1.02806
135	135	0.982155
135	180	0.946621
180	0	0.78688
180	45	0.770394
180	90	0.729059
180	135	0.685236
180	180	0.66624

Table 2: Effective Neutrino mass for Normal Mass hierarchy and Maximum CP Violating case. Input value are given in ref[16]

Majorana phase	Majorana phase	Effective neutrino masses
α in degrees	β in degrees	m_{ee} in eV
0	0	1.94058
0	45	1.89747
0	90	1.87932
0	135	1.89747
0	180	1.94058
45	0	1.82864
45	45	1.78282
45	90	1.75488
45	135	1.76218
45	180	1.80012
90	0	1.49059
90	45	1.44454
90	90	1.40991
90	135	1.40827
90	180	1.44066
135	0	1.02806
135	45	0.982155
135	90	0.946621
135	135	0.94417
135	180	0.976441
180	0	0.729059
180	45	0.685236
180	90	0.66624
180	135	0.685237
180	180	0.729061

Table 3: Effective Neutrino mass for inverted mass hierarchy and CP conserving. Input value are given in ref[16]

Majorana phase in degrees	Majorana phase	Effective neutrino masses
α in degrees	β in degrees	m_{ee} in eV
0	0	1.99993
0	45	1.98273
0	90	1.94058
0	135	1.89749
0	180	1.87935
45	0	1.87207
45	45	1.8652
45	90	1.82863
45	135	1.78284
45	180	1.75491
90	0	1.51986
90	45	1.5212
90	90	1.49057
90	135	1.44455
90	180	1.40994
135	0	1.05556
135	45	1.05775
135	90	1.02805
135	135	0.982163
135	180	0.946648
180	0	0.78685
180	45	0.770372
180	90	0.729057
180	135	0.685255
180	180	0.66627

Table 4: Effective Neutrino mass for Inverted Mass hierarchy and Maximum CP Violating case. Input value are given in ref[16]

Majorana phase	Majorana phase	Effective neutrino masses
α in degrees	β in degrees	m_{ee} in eV
0	0	1.94058
0	45	1.89749
0	90	1.87935
0	135	1.89749
0	180	1.94058
45	0	1.82863
45	45	1.78284
45	90	1.75491
45	135	1.76221
45	180	1.80013
90	0	1.49057
90	45	1.44455
90	90	1.40994
90	135	1.4083
90	180	1.44067
135	0	1.02805
135	45	0.982163
135	90	0.946648
135	135	0.944198
135	180	0.976452
180	0	0.729057
180	45	0.685255
180	90	0.66627
180	135	0.685257
180	180	0.729058

Here $\beta = 0^0$ and α is varying $[0,180]$ for Δm_{31} positive

Here $\beta = 0^0$ and α is varying $[0,180]$ for Δm_{31} negative

Here $\beta = 90^0$ and α is varying $[0,180]$ for Δm_{31} negative

Here $\beta = 90^0$ and α is varying $[0,180]$ for Δm_{31} positive

Here $\beta = 180^0$ and α is varying $[0,180]$ for Δm_{31} positive

Here $\beta = 180^0$ and α is varying $[0,180]$ for Δm_{31} negative

5.

5. Conclusions

Future and present search for neutrinoless double beta decay purpose at probing lepton number violation and the Majorana nature of neutrinos with remarkable precision. Several experimental programs are currently under discussion. We find for the maximum CP violation case effective electron neutrino mass $m_{ee} = (0.66624 - 1.94058)$ eV for normal mass and $(0.66627 - 1.94058)$ for inverted mass hierarchy spectrum. In CP conserving case effective electron neutrino mass $m_{ee} = (0.66624 - 1.99996)$ eV, for normal and $(0.66627 - 1.99993)$ for inverted mass hierarchy spectrum.

We have calculated the effect of CP violation in effective neutrino mass for specific choice of Majorana phases. We have found due to nonzero value of Majorana phases, effective neutrino masses suppress.

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